

ISOTROPIC AND NEARLY ISOTROPIC FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

It has recently been demonstrated in some considerable detail that a fibre composite with isotropic elastic properties can be realised with a number of different arrangements of fibres. In all cases the volume fraction of fibres which can be introduced into the composite is limited. In the case of an isotropic arrangement the largest volume fraction which can be attained is about 50%. The elastic properties of this arrangement, which consists of two sets of fibres, one set parallel to cube edges and the other parallel to cube diagonals, is explored in detail. Its properties are compared with a more symmetric arrangement which is close to but not completely isotropic, namely, one in which fibres are arranged parallel to the six cube face diagonals. A very useful arrangement is that in which, for the first case, one of the sets of fibres parallel to cube edges is omitted. The properties of these isotropic and nearly isotropic fibre arrangements are compared with the properties of particulate composites.

KEYWORDS : fiber, isotropic , elastic properties

1. INTRODUCTION

The advantages of isotropy or near isotropy of the elastic moduli of a fibre composite are great. First, apart from the obvious simplification of design calculations, thick specimens may be made and used: this is not possible with laminates. Since the elastic properties of an anisotropic material are represented by a fourth-order tensor, isotropy or near isotropy of this leads to the isotropy of properties represented by lower-order tensors, e.g. the thermal and transport properties. Hence, problems of internal stresses between laminations, and particularly differential thermal contraction effects, are eliminated. In addition, fibrous anisotropic composites can be expected to be much more damage tolerant than their particulate counterparts.

2. TRULY ISOTROPIC ARRANGEMENTS WITH SIX FIBRE DIRECTIONS

If fibres are arranged to run in six directions, each set normal to the faces of a regular dodecahedron, then elastic isotropy results, with

$$C_{11} = C_{22} = C_{33} = \frac{1}{5} E V_f, \quad C_{12} = C_{13} = C_{23} = C_{44} = C_{55} = C_{66} = \frac{1}{15} E V_f,$$

where E is Young's modulus of the fibres and V_f is their volume fraction. The array includes cubic symmetry and $C_{12} = C_{44}$, but the ratio C_{11} to C_{12} is 3, hence permitting $C_{11} - C_{12} = 2C_{44}$. That such a three-dimensional array of fibres is elastically isotropic has been proved by Christensen [1]. The result is stated without a direct proof by Rosen & Shu [2] who also cite an unpublished report by Dow et al [3]. They state that elastic isotropy would be obtained if fibres ran in six directions, each passing through a vertex of a regular icosahedron and, they go on, 'it does not appear possible to construct a continuum space lattice'. They recognised that the same six directions are defined by the normals to the faces of a regular dodecahedron. It is stated without proof by Tarnopols'kii and co-workers (Tarnopols'kii et al [4]). It also appears from records in our possession that early in 1970, H L Cox was aware that isotropy could be produced by fibres running normal to the faces of a regular dodecahedron, parallel to cube edges and cube body diagonals in the correct proportions, i.e. in seven directions, parallel to cube edges and cube face diagonals, i.e. in nine directions, as well as equally arranged in twelve directions.

Fibres arranged normal to the faces of either the regular dodecahedron or the regular icosahedron will show elastic isotropy of the type to be considered here with fibres running in six directions for the dodecahedron and in ten for the icosahedron. The question to be answered in these two cases is : what is the practically attainable volume fraction? Parkhouse and Kelly [5] show that for the former a volume fraction of about 0.25 is the highest that can be obtained; and if it were, the instructions to a machine to provide fibres in the correct relative orientations would be difficult though not impossible.

In view of this they go on to show that isotropy may be obtained with fibres in seven directions and for this case that a volume fraction of 0.5 is attainable. The array consists of fibres parallel to cube edges and also parallel to cube body diagonals. Provided that $\frac{2}{5}$ of the fibre material is in the former orientation and $\frac{3}{5}$ is in the latter, isotropy is ensured. This seven-directional arrangement is attractive for its versatility; where isotropy is not required the proportions of material in each direction may be varied. It will come as no surprise to designers of latticed decks that a particularly attractive arrangement for a fibre-reinforced plate could be achieved by concentrating the fibres parallel to two edge directions, omitting fibres from the third edge direction and providing fibres in the diagonal directions as shear reinforcement. This six-directional arrangement is capable of transmitting all loading, both in-plane and out-of-plane, through its reinforcement alone, not requiring the matrix to provide a primary load path.

In this paper we compare such an arrangement with another array of fibres in six directions, namely parallel to cube face diagonals or equivalently, parallel to the normals to the faces of a regular rhombic dodecahedron.

3. NEARLY ISOTROPIC ARRANGEMENT WITH SIX FIBRE DIRECTIONS

When fibres run in the six directions each normal to the face of a rhombic dodecahedron (i.e. parallel to the diagonals of cube faces) we can find the elastic constants very easily with the result

$$\sigma^T = \frac{V_f E}{6} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & 1 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix} \varepsilon^T, \quad (1)$$

where σ^T is the stress tensor and ε^T the strain tensor. This array is cubic and hence the S_{ij} are $S_{11} = 9/(V_f E)$, $S_{12} = -3/(V_f E)$, $S_{44} = 12/(V_f E)$. From these we immediately find, using standard results for cubic crystals, that the Young's modulus parallel to the edges of the cubic cell is $\frac{1}{9} V_f E$, the minimum value. Parallel to a cube diagonal the (maximum) value is $\frac{1}{5} V_f E$, and parallel to a cube face diagonal (i.e. parallel to one of the sets of fibres) is $\frac{1}{6} V_f E$. The ratio of the maximum to the minimum value for the Young's modulus is 1.8.

The values of the shear moduli, again in the absence of a matrix, it should be remembered, are as follows: for shear on a face of the unit cube in any direction the shear modulus equals C_{44} , i.e. $\frac{1}{12} V_f E$ which is the maximum value; for shear parallel to one set of fibres on a plane passing through four opposing vertices of the cube the shear modulus is $\frac{1}{24} V_f E$; the minimum value. The shear modulus when shearing in the direction of a cube diagonal is $\frac{1}{20} V_f E$. There is just one bulk modulus for every possible arrangement of fibres loaded uniaxially, which is $\frac{1}{9} V_f E$. The value of the Poisson's ratio for tension parallel to a cube edge is $\frac{1}{3}$ and in a direction parallel to a cube diagonal is $\frac{1}{5}$. Only for these two directions is the Poisson's ratio isotropic in the plane normal to the direction of tension. The ratio of the maximum value of Young's modulus to the minimum value of the shear modulus is $\frac{24}{5}$ which, it might be noted, is almost double the corresponding value $\frac{5}{2}$ for the fully isotropic case (see next section). Parkhouse and Kelly [5] show that a volume fraction as high as $\frac{5}{8}$ may be obtained with this fibre array, and that is the value used in section 8.

4. COMPOSITE WITH SEVEN FIBRE DIRECTIONS

If a volume fraction V_e of fibres are distributed equally in three directions parallel to the edges of a cube, the array of stiffness constants is of the form:

$$\sigma^T = \frac{1}{3} V_e \begin{pmatrix} E_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & E_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \varepsilon^T$$

(2)

E_1, E_2, E_3 are the respective tensile Young's moduli for fibres arranged parallel to the axes 1, 2 and 3, respectively. We write the matrix so that the result of omitting one set of fibres by setting one of the fibre moduli to zero is obvious. Similarly, if a volume fraction V_d fibres are distributed equally in four directions parallel to the cube body diagonals we will have

$$\sigma^T = \frac{1}{9} V_d \begin{pmatrix} E_d & E_d & E_d & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ E_d & E_d & E_d & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ E_d & E_d & E_d & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & E_d & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & E_d & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & E_d \end{pmatrix} \varepsilon^T \quad (3)$$

Adding (2) and (3) leads to

$$\sigma^T = \frac{1}{9} \begin{pmatrix} V_d E_d + 3V_e E_1 & V_d E_d & V_d E_d & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ V_d E_d & V_d E_d + 3V_e E_2 & V_d E_d & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ V_d E_d & V_d E_d & V_d E_d + 3V_e E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & V_d E_d & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & V_d E_d & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & V_d E_d \end{pmatrix} \varepsilon^T \quad (4)$$

It is worth noting that on setting $E_1 = E_2 = E_3 = E_d = E$, $V_e = \frac{2}{5}V_f$ and $V_d = \frac{3}{5}V_f$ the stress-strain relation (4) is then isotropic such that Young's modulus is $\frac{1}{6}V_f E$, Poisson's ratio is $\frac{1}{4}$ and the shear modulus is $\frac{1}{15}V_f E$.

5. SIX FIBRE DIRECTIONS : ANISOTROPIC CASE

Consider the case, important in practice, of omitting one set of fibres parallel to one of the cube edges, say direction 3. Then we have

$$\sigma^T = \frac{1}{9} \begin{pmatrix} V_d E_d + 3V_e E_1 & V_d E_d & V_d E_d & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ V_d E_d & V_d E_d + 3V_e E_2 & V_d E_d & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ V_d E_d & V_d E_d & V_d E_d & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & V_d E_d & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & V_d E_d & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & V_d E_d \end{pmatrix} \varepsilon^T \quad (5)$$

This array is approximately isotropic except for stretches along the directions 1 or 2. The inverse relation is given by

$$\varepsilon^T = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{3}{V_e E_1} & 0 & -\frac{3}{V_e E_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{3}{V_e E_2} & -\frac{3}{V_e E_2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{3}{V_e E_1} & -\frac{3}{V_e E_2} & \frac{9}{V_d E_d} + \frac{3}{V_e E_1} + \frac{3}{V_e E_2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{9}{V_d E_d} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{9}{V_d E_d} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{9}{V_d E_d} \end{pmatrix} \sigma^T$$

(6)

The shear modulus on a face of the cube is $\frac{1}{9}V_d E_d$. Young's modulus in the 1-direction is $\frac{1}{3}V_e E_1$, in the 2-direction is $\frac{1}{3}V_e E_2$, and in the 3-direction is

$$\frac{1}{\frac{9}{V_d E_d} + \frac{3}{V_e E_1} + \frac{3}{V_e E_2}}.$$

On setting $E_1 = E_2 = E_d = E$ the Young's modulus of the fibres in the composite in the 1 and 2 directions is $\frac{1}{3}V_e E$ and in the 3 direction it is

$$\frac{1}{3}V_e E \left(\frac{V_d}{3V_e + 2V_d} \right).$$

In section 4 we considered fibres in seven directions, and here we are omitting fibres solely along one cube axis. The volume fraction attainable with $V_e = \frac{2}{3}V_d$ was shown by Parkhouse and Kelly [4] to be close to $\frac{1}{2}$; actually $\frac{15}{8}[2 - \sqrt{3}] = 0.5024$. In what follows we shall refer to this volume fraction as V_i .

Now take $V_e = \frac{2}{3}V_d$ and $V_i = \frac{1}{2}$ rather than 0.5024, so that $V_e = \frac{1}{5}$ and $V_d = \frac{3}{10}$ such that $V_i = V_e + V_d = \frac{1}{2}$ as required. Omitting fibres in just one edge direction, then results in a total volume fraction of $V_f = \frac{2}{3}V_e + V_d = \frac{13}{30}$ ($\cong 0.433$). We then have a Young's modulus $\frac{E}{15} = \frac{2}{13}V_e E$ in the 1 and 2 directions, and $\frac{E}{60} = \frac{1}{26}V_e E$ in the 3 direction for which the Poisson's ratio is $\frac{1}{4}$. Young's modulus for the direction of the principal cube diagonal is $\frac{3E}{40} = \frac{9}{52}V_e E$ (determined numerically). The shear modulus parallel to a face of the cube is $\frac{E}{30} = \frac{1}{13}V_e E$ (i.e. $\frac{1}{9}V_d E_d$) and the value along the principal cube diagonal is $0.013E = 0.0239V_e E$ (determined numerically). When this fibre array is used to calculate the elastic moduli, including the contribution of the matrix, the total fibre volume fraction is $V_f = \frac{13}{30} \cong 0.433$, and hence that of the matrix is $V_m = 1 - V_f = \frac{17}{30} \cong 0.567$.

6. A CONTRIBUTION FROM THE MATRIX

We now describe an approximate scheme for adding the contribution of the matrix. The approach is to assume that the fibres and the matrix in the composite are subject to the same uniform strain field. It follows that the corresponding displacement field will also be uniform, and continuous throughout the composite. The corresponding stress field will however be such that the tractions on the fibre/matrix interfaces will be discontinuous, indicating why the approach is approximate. The imposition of continuous tractions at the fibre/matrix interfaces leads to localised strain concentrations which are being neglected. However, it is expected that the approximation will be suitable for predicting the values of the moduli when the fibre and matrix moduli have similar values. If this is not the case, and the matrix modulus is much less than that of the fibre, the methodology is expected to provide valuable information regarding the expected degree of anisotropy for the various fibre configurations considered in this paper.

Because the strain field is assumed uniform throughout the composite, it is possible to consider the behaviour of the fibres and matrix separately. The effects of the fibres alone, when subject to a uniform strain field, have already been considered in sections 2-4. Consider now the matrix alone whose geometry corresponds to a monolithic sample of matrix in which there are now cylindrical holes at locations where the fibres were found in the composite. As this matrix sample is considered to have the same uniform strain field as the fibres, the effective elastic constants can be estimated by splitting

the problem into two parts which are easily analysed. The elastic properties of the matrix portion of the composite are identical to those of a solid monolithic sample of matrix, less the elastic properties of an assembly of fibres made of matrix material which are located where the cylindrical holes are encountered. The elastic properties of the monolithic matrix are assumed to be given, and those for the assembly of fibres having matrix properties are easily calculated using the analysis given in sections 2-4. To express the approach mathematically, let C_{ijkl}^{matrix} denote the isotropic elastic coefficients of a homogeneous sample of matrix, let C_{ijkl} denote the elastic constants for the composite, let C_{ijkl}^f denote the elastic constants for the assembly of fibres alone, and let C_{ijkl}^m denote the elastic constants for the corresponding assembly of fibres made of matrix material. It then follows that

$$C_{ijkl} = V_f C_{ijkl}^f + C_{ijkl}^{\text{matrix}} - V_f C_{ijkl}^m . \quad (8)$$

The first term in (8) obviously arises from consideration of the fibres in the composite, the second term is that for a homogeneous sample of matrix material, and the third term arises from a consideration of the effective properties of fibres made of matrix material having the same volume fraction and arrangement as the fibres. The elastic coefficients C_{ijkl}^{matrix} for the isotropic matrix are given, in terms of the matrix shear modulus G_m and Poisson's ratio ν_m , in the form of the following stress-strain relations,

$$\sigma^T = \frac{2G_m}{1-2\nu_m} \begin{pmatrix} 1-\nu_m & \nu_m & \nu_m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \nu_m & 1-\nu_m & \nu_m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \nu_m & \nu_m & 1-\nu_m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1-2\nu_m}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1-2\nu_m}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1-2\nu_m}{2} \end{pmatrix} \varepsilon^T . \quad (9)$$

In order to calculate the various moduli that are associated with the elastic constants defined by (8) for the various cases discussed in this paper it is essential to be able to invert a stress-strain relation of the form

$$\sigma^T = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha + \beta_1 & \alpha & \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha & \alpha + \beta_2 & \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha & \alpha & \alpha + \beta_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G \end{pmatrix} \varepsilon^T . \quad (10)$$

It can be shown that the Young's moduli (in the cube edge directions) for the composite arising from stress-strain relations of the form (10) are given by

$$E_1 = \frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta_1} + \frac{1}{\beta_2} + \frac{1}{\beta_3}}{\frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta_2} + \frac{1}{\beta_3}} \beta_1, \quad E_2 = \frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta_1} + \frac{1}{\beta_2} + \frac{1}{\beta_3}}{\frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta_1} + \frac{1}{\beta_3}} \beta_2, \quad E_3 = \frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta_1} + \frac{1}{\beta_2} + \frac{1}{\beta_3}}{\frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\beta_1} + \frac{1}{\beta_2}} \beta_3. \quad (11)$$

The relations (11) are used in section 8 to estimate the Young's moduli for various fibre composites when taking account of the presence of the matrix.

In order to quantify the degree of anisotropy more completely we shall be interested in the values of Young's modulus and the shear modulus for the additional directions defined by the face diagonals of a cube and also the cube diagonals. The calculation of these values has been achieved by developing a general computer program applicable for any numbers of fibres aligned in any number of directions. The elastic constants can be calculated for any orientation of the Cartesian reference axes.

7. PARTICULATE COMPOSITES

One way in principle to reinforce in an isotropic manner is to use approximately equiaxed particles. The maximum volume fraction obtainable in practice is close to $\frac{5}{8}$ (Milewski [6]) ; almost the same as that obtained for the arrangement given in section 3 above and is the value used in Table 1. Hashin and Shtrikman [7] (see also review by Hashin [8]) have developed methods of calculating the effective elastic properties of statistically isotropic composites based on reinforcement with spherical particles. He provides the following upper and lower bounds for the bulk and shear moduli of the composite denoted by K_c and G_c respectively, made of two phases having bulk moduli K_1 and K_2 , and shear moduli G_1 and G_2

$$K_-^c = K_1 + \frac{V_2}{\frac{1}{K_2 - K_1} + \frac{3V_1}{3K_1 + 4G_1}},$$

$$K_+^c = K_2 + \frac{V_1}{\frac{1}{K_1 - K_2} + \frac{3V_2}{3K_2 + 4G_2}},$$
(12)

$$G_-^c = G_1 + \frac{V_2}{\frac{1}{G_2 - G_1} + \frac{6V_1(K_1 + 2G_1)}{5G_1(3K_1 + 4G_1)}},$$

$$G_+^c = G_2 + \frac{V_1}{\frac{1}{G_1 - G_2} + \frac{6V_2(K_2 + 2G_2)}{5G_2(3K_2 + 4G_2)}},$$
(13)

where it has been assumed that $K_1 < K_2$ and $G_1 < G_2$. Two corresponding values for each of the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio are found on substituting G_+^c, K_+^c and G_-^c, K_-^c into the well known relations

$$E = \frac{9KG}{3K+G}, \quad \nu = \frac{3K-2G}{2(3K+G)}.$$
(14)

The values of K_1, K_2, G_1 and G_2 needed when using (12) and (13) are calculated from values of E and ν for the fibre and matrix using the well known inverted forms of (14), namely

$$K = \frac{E}{3(1-2\nu)}, \quad G = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)}.$$

8. COMPARISON OF VALUES OBTAINABLE FOR FIBRE AND PARTICULATE COMPOSITES

We consider now various types of composite where the reinforcements are silicon carbide and glass in both particulate and fibre form, and where the matrices are an aluminium alloy and an epoxy. The properties assumed are :

Silicon carbide (particulate & fibre)	$E = 400$ GPa	$\nu = 0.28$
Aluminium alloy (6061)	$E = 70$ GPa	$\nu = 0.30$
Glass (fibre)	$E = 74$ GPa	$\nu = 0.20$
Epoxy	$E = 3.89$ GPa	$\nu = 0.37$

When presenting the results of predictions, the parameters E_1 , E_2 , and E_3 denote the Young's moduli in the 1, 2 and 3 directions of a cube while G_1 , G_2 , and G_3 denote the corresponding shear moduli. The subscript 'face' is attached to E and G to denote that the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio are for pure axial and shear loading along a diagonal of a cube face. The subscript 'diag' is attached to E and G to denote that the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio are for pure axial and shear loading along a diagonal of a cube.

Fibres parallel to faces of rhombic dodecahedron (section 3)

Using the results given in section 6, it is possible derive for the composite expressions for the Young's moduli E_1^c , E_2^c , and E_3^c and the shear modulus G for this type of composite using (10) and (11). The parameters α , β_1 , β_2 , β_3 and G for this case are

$$\alpha = \frac{V_f(E_f - E_m)}{12} + \frac{2G_m v_m}{1 - 2v_m}, \quad \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \frac{V_f(E_f - E_m)}{12} + 2G_m, \quad G = \frac{V_f(E_f - E_m)}{12} + G_m.$$

Predictions based on these expressions and the relations (11) for the case $V_f = 0.625$ are given in Table 1. The differences between the Young's moduli, and shear moduli, for the cube edges, faces and diagonal directions indicate the degree of anisotropy.

Fibres parallel to three cube edges and all body diagonals (section 4)

Using the results given in section 6, for the isotropic case where $E_1 = E_2 = E_3 = E_d = E$, $V_e = \frac{2}{5}V_f$ and $V_d = \frac{3}{5}V_f$, it is possible derive expressions for the Young's moduli E_1^c , E_2^c , and E_3^c and the shear modulus for this type of composite using the formulae

$$\alpha = \frac{V_f(E_f - E_m)}{15} + \frac{2G_m v_m}{1 - 2v_m}, \quad \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \frac{2V_f(E_f - E_m)}{15} + 2G_m, \quad G = \frac{V_f(E_f - E_m)}{15} + G_m.$$

Predictions based on these expressions and the relations (11) for the case $V_f = 0.5$ are given in Table 1 which indicate perfect isotropy.

Fibres parallel to two cube edges and all body diagonals (section 5)

Using the results given in section 6, expressions for the Young's moduli E_1^c , E_2^c , and E_3^c and the shear modulus are derived for this type of composite using

$$\alpha = \frac{V_f(E_f - E_m)}{13} + \frac{2G_m v_m}{1 - 2v_m}, \quad \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \frac{2V_f(E_f - E_m)}{13} + 2G_m, \\ \beta_3 = 2G_m, \quad G = \frac{V_f(E_f - E_m)}{13} + G_m.$$

Predictions based on these expressions and the relations (11) for the case $V_f = 0.433$ are given in Table 1. The quantities E_{face} and G_{face} are for the cube face diagonal that bisects the angle between the 1 and 2 directions. The differences between the Young's moduli, and shear moduli, for the cube edges, faces and diagonal directions again indicate the degree of anisotropy.

Particulate composites

For particulate composites, the use of the bounds derived by Hashin and Shtrikman [7] leads to two predictions for Young's modulus E^c and shear modulus G^c of the composite. The shear moduli are in fact upper and lower bounds. The results of applying the analysis given in section 7 are shown in Table 1 where the volume fraction of particulate reinforcement has been taken to be $\frac{5}{8}$ and $\frac{1}{2}$ so that direct comparisons can be made between the nearly isotropic six fibre direction composite and the truly isotropic composite.

The large difference shown in Table 1 between the bounds for the moduli, estimated for isotropic particulate composites made of silicon carbide reinforced aluminium and glass reinforced epoxy, and the moduli for the corresponding fibre reinforced composites is a consequence of the neglect of strain concentrations at fibre/matrix interfaces. Their effect is particularly important when the matrix modulus is relatively high and significantly different from that of the fibres, as is the case for silicon carbide fibre reinforced by aluminium alloy.

9. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The moduli for the particulate case do in fact agree with experiment to the extent that experimental values lie within predicted bounds for cases of both large and small ratios of moduli. In the case of fully aligned fibres the neglect of the inter-phase stresses on the modulus parallel to the fibres is not large as the mixtures rule is a very good estimate. Hill and others have given bounds and they are not far apart. For non-aligned fibres, and in particular for the 3-D arrangements which we are considering in this paper, the effect of inter-phase stresses appears to be large if the fibre and matrix moduli differ widely, and may be larger than expected for the cases of more similar moduli. We can therefore only compare the results for the various fibre cases among themselves as we have only managed to develop a rather approximate solution when taking account of the effect of the matrix. Such a comparison does however enable us to estimate the degree of anisotropy that results from the various fibre configurations. At this time we cannot compare this with a much more sophisticated consideration of the effect of the matrix which, while not exact for any particular case does give well established theoretical bounds when the reinforcement is particulate or fully aligned in a single direction, e.g. those of Hashin and others.

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	V_f	SiC/Al	SiC/Epoxy	Glass/Al	Glass/Epoxy
Nearly isotropic - 6 directions	0.625				
E_1, E_2, E_3		93	31.42	70.28	8.77
E_{face}		106.59	45.75	70.46	11.59
E_{diag}		112.05	53.95	70.51	12.99
G_1, G_2, G_3, G_{face}		44.11	22.05	27.13	5.07
G_{diag}		37.98	13.90	27.06	3.69
Isotropic - 7 directions	0.5				
$E_1, E_2, E_3, E_{face}, E_{diag}$		97.67	37.16	70.34	9.88
$G_1, G_2, G_3, G_{face}, G_{diag}$		37.92	14.62	27.06	3.76
Anisotropic - 6 directions	0.433				
E_1, E_2, E_{face}		95.37	31.50	70.31	9.07
E_3		75.67	10.75	70.07	5.20
E_{diag}		97.10	35.15	70.33	9.74
G_1, G_2, G_3, G_{face}		37.92	14.62	27.06	3.76
G_{diag}		32.51	6.13	27.00	2.46
Particulate	0.625				
E_{max}		233.54	184.93	72.74	37.04
E_{min}		180.15	16.81	72.73	14.34
G_{max}		91.67	73.52	29.306	15.12
G_{min}		70.43	6.35	29.305	5.47
Particulate	0.5				
E_{max}		192.43	136.88	72.25	28.47
E_{min}		146.31	11.76	72.24	10.57
G_{max}		75.5	54.58	28.814	11.52
G_{min}		57.09	4.42	28.813	3.99

Table 1 : Predictions of moduli